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The Effect of Environmental Disaster on International Politics

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ABSTRACT

Today, "global environmental issues have attracted an increasing amount of attention from the international community," introducing new topics for international politics. The rise of global environmental issues has raised the status of scientists in international politics, "challenging the traditional concept of national sovereignty, national security, and national interests." "International organizations are required to play a greater role, but the current anarchy of the international community makes it very difficult to solve global environmental problems."

Keywords

International Politics; Global Environmental Issues; Effect; Influence

1. The Rise of global environmental problems

"We live in an era of interdependence". In today's globalization, the interaction between man and man, man and society, man and nature are getting closer and closer, but "the two worlds of human life - the biosphere he inherited and the technological sphere he created - have lost balance and are in potential profound contradictions".

Environment, in a broad sense, refers to the material environment for human survival, that is, the living place and resources for human survival. As far as human living environment is concerned, it generally includes natural environment and man-made environment. The global environmental problems we are discussing here are mainly man-made environmental problems. "Environmental problems refer to the changes in environmental quality caused by human activities on the environment that are not conducive to human beings, and the problems that these changes endanger human beings and development. It includes two basic aspects: one is the destruction of the natural environment; the other is environmental pollution." Environmental

problems do not all enter the field of international politics. Only those environmental damage beyond national boundaries and solving these environmental problems that need to involve transnational activities can have international political significance. Therefore, global environmental problems refer to a series of environmental problems facing the contemporary international community that transcend national and regional boundaries and are caused by human activities acting on the global environment, which are related to the survival and development of the whole mankind.

The entry of environmental issues into the field of international politics is not a contemporary phenomenon. Since the end of the 19th century, Mahan's sea power theory, Mackinder's continental heart theory and Haushofer's living space theory all emphasize the important and even decisive influence of geographical environment factors on a country's foreign policy and international relations. They mainly look at this issue from a strategic perspective from the perspective of the survival of a single country. However, the environmental theory appeared in the 1970s and 1980s has changed in content and foothold. Since the 1970s, with the rapid development of science and technology, especially media technology, a series of global environmental problems have increasingly attracted global attention. For example, the environmental deterioration of the atmosphere and space, water pollution, soil degradation, the loss of forests and the destruction of biodiversity, solid waste and nuclear pollution are posing a serious threat to human survival and development. Global environmental issues have increasingly become an important issue in today's world. In this case, the club of Rome published two research reports, the limit of growth in 1972 and mankind at a turning point in 1974, indicating that global environmental problems began to enter the field of international politics. Through the unremitting efforts of other organizations such as the United Nations, the world watch Institute and the Brandt Committee, the status of the "low-level politics" of global environmental issues has risen in the eyes of contemporary scholars and politicians.

2. Characteristics of global environmental problems

Global environmental problems are the product of the interaction between man and nature, which reflects the contradiction between man and man, man, and society. Global environmental problems have the following characteristics.

2.1 Global environmental problems are worldwide.

Global environmental problems are worldwide in scale, scope, and solutions. The cosmopolitanism of scale means that it has a world dimension in terms of existence space and impact consequences. No matter where you are on the earth, you will be affected by global environmental problems. For example: "although Greenland is far from any source of atmospheric lead pollution, the amount of lead deposited in Greenland ice has increased by 300% per year since 1940." the worldwide scope refers to that some environmental problems are regional in phenomenon, and the consequence relates to the whole international community, so that regional environmental problems have global significance. For example, the destruction of tropical rain forests

mainly occurs in developing countries such as Brazil, Indonesia, and the Democratic Republic of the Congo, but the impact is worldwide. The destruction of large-scale tropical rain forests will increase the degree of the earth's greenhouse effect and emission phenomenon, destroy the normal climate and biodiversity, and thus threaten the whole mankind. The universality of solutions means that the solution of these global environmental problems cannot be completed by any single country but requires the cooperation of all countries in the world. For example, fluoride, which is widely used in industry in developing countries, will be phased out, which is the main reason for the gradual destruction of fluoride in the atmosphere.

2.2 The impact of global environmental problems is long-term.

The emergence of global environmental problems is a relatively long process of gradual accumulation. The environmental problems we are facing may be the result of human activities in recent years, decades or even centuries. Many processes that eventually lead to ecosystem collapse are gradual. Before they fall into difficulties and disasters, they can rarely attract enough attention. The impact of global environmental problems is also long-term. They are not only a threat to contemporary people, but also a threat to future generations. Global environmental problems cannot be solved immediately, and their solution process is long-term. Even if environmental problems such as desertification and wetland damage can be recovered, they still need to pay a huge price and make unremitting efforts for a long time. Some global environmental problems such as species extinction are irreversible and unrecoverable.

2.3 Global environmental issues transcend ideology.

Global environmental problems "do not exist because you are a socialist country, nor can they be avoided because you are a developed country". The existence of global environmental problems is a common threat to all countries in the world. For all countries, it is not a "zero sum" game, either a "win-win" game or a "double lose" game. Solving global environmental problems should be the common interests of all countries in the world. Facing this problem, it is difficult to understand it with rigid ideological vision and cold war thinking. It requires us to overcome the prejudice of groups, nations, and countries, transcend ideological differences, strengthen cooperation from the perspective of human "class" and jointly promote the solution of global environmental problems.

2.4 Global environmental issues are complex.

"The first law of ecology is that everything is related to other things." the global environmental problems arising from the era of global interdependence have internal relations. They are interrelated and form a complex and indivisible system. Every problem is related to any other problem, and every clear solution to one problem will worsen or interfere with other problems. In this way, using the linear or sequential method of "treating head pain and foot pain" in the past cannot solve these problems. We must examine global

environmental problems from the perspective of system theory and formulate strategies for overall and comprehensive treatment of problems.

3. The impact of global environmental problems on international politics

New problems need new ideas. The rise of global environmental problems, a new problem faced by the international community, has had an important impact on the theory and practice of traditional international politics.

3.1 The rise of global environmental problems challenges national sovereignty.

The state is the most basic actor in international politics. The nation-state in the modern sense began with the Westphalia peace treaty in 1648. The central principle of this peace treaty is simple and clear: the ruler of a territory should decide the religion in the territory. The principle of national sovereignty was also established. As the fundamental attribute of the state, sovereignty is defined by the French philosopher Jean Bodin as "the highest power of the state to control its public and subjects without legal constraints." sovereignty includes "internal sovereignty, that is, it enjoys the highest authority within its territory and among its citizens" and "external sovereignty, that is, no country is superior to other countries. National sovereignty, including internal sovereignty and external sovereignty, has two levels of norms and facts". (PS) sovereignty is supreme, exclusive, and indivisible. The sovereign attribute of the state makes the international system composed of sovereign states in a state of anarchy. The essence of the "anarchy" international system is: "there is no authority that can command the state how to behave; no actor has legal authority to tell the state what to do." is a term that "in political science, it does not mean a state of chaos as commonly known, but only a lack of government that can manage effectively".

National sovereignty, the basic concept of traditional international politics, requires the state to have exclusive power in the management of domestic affairs. However, in the face of global environmental problems, national sovereignty increasingly shows the limitations of the times. The traditional concept of national sovereignty makes it difficult to coordinate actions among countries. The sovereign state system has become the most important obstacle to the management of global ecological and environmental problems. The emergence of global environmental problems increasingly calls for countries all over the world to go beyond the boundaries of nation-state, carry out international cooperation and jointly manage global environmental problems. In this case, more and more international environmental cooperation mechanisms have been established and strengthened, and more and more international organizations participate in the management of international environmental affairs and play a more and more important role. In this process, national sovereignty is increasingly shared and restricted, which in fact challenges the supremacy, exclusivity, and indivisibility of national sovereignty.

3.2. The rise of global environmental problems has an impact on the traditional concept of security.

Security "means that there is no threat objectively and no fear subjectively". In international politics, security is a basic concept and a basic goal. For a country, the pursuit of security is the most important thing at any time. It constitutes the most fundamental reason for its own existence. Security has the highest priority because of the anarchy of sovereign states and the international system composed of sovereign states.

The traditional security concept is centered on the state and military. They believe that in the anarchy of the international community, there is always the possibility of war between countries; The state is the main body of security, and national security is competitive; National interests are the goal of security, and the use of military force is the means of security. "If a country is not worried about sacrificing its core values to avoid war, and if its core values are challenged and a war occurs, it can win the war, then the country is safe," Lipman said Carl Deutsch said: "security means peace and the maintenance of peace." Barry Buzan defined security as "the pursuit of freedom from threats", realizing "national and territorial integrity and the ability to oppose hostile forces" and "the bottom line of security is survival".

The emergence of global environmental problems has brought great impact to the traditional concept of security.

First, the emergence of global environmental problems requires the expansion of the content of the concept of security. Global environmental problems can directly have a huge impact on security. For example, in 1986, the Chernobyl nuclear power plant exploded, and its radioactive cloud spread to Western Europe and other places, causing about 8000 people to die from radiation or various diseases, and the casualties are no less than a war. Global environmental problems can also indirectly bring problems to security. For example, Mexico has about 1000 square miles of land desertification every year, which brings huge losses to the country's agriculture, causing many people to flow into the United States bordering it to survive, which has a great negative impact on the national security of the United States. Therefore, there is constant friction between the United States and Mexico. Because of this, environmental security has become an important aspect of the concept of security. "Some analysts call 'environmental security' the 'ultimate security', which" is related to the place as the basic support system and the biosphere of the whole planet, and it depends on all other human undertakings ". In addition to military security and environmental security, economic security, political security, and social security should also be the contents of security.

Secondly, the emergence of global environmental problems requires the multi-level of security subjects. The global nature of global environmental issues shows that security subjects include not only countries, but also the world, that is, global security, common security, comprehensive security, and human security. "Similarly, the world will also be affected by other regions, other countries, local departments and individuals. Security is connected to a wider global network of relationships." Therefore, in addition to global and national security subjects, there should also be regions, departments, and individuals. In a sense, security is ultimately only implemented to specific individuals.

Finally, the rise of global environmental problems requires changing the way to achieve security. In the face of global problems that are worldwide, long-term, beyond ideology and complexity, it is impossible to achieve them through the competitive and military means in the past. Global environmental problems make it impossible for the security of one country to be based on the insecurity of other countries. This requires the establishment of a common concept of security through international cooperation.

3.3 The rise of global environmental problems challenges the traditional concept of national interests.

National interest is one of the core concepts in the theoretical research of international relations. "It refers to some basic principles for a state to protect itself and its nation from foreign aggression in complex international relations". In anarchy, "politicians think and act according to the interests defined by power". In international politics, national interest is the guidepost for analyzing national behavior and an important basis and decisive factor for a country to set foreign goals.

The traditional view of national interests defines national interests from the perspective of their own countries. For example, Hans Morgenthau believes that "national interests should include three important aspects: territorial integrity, national sovereignty and cultural integrity." the emergence of global environmental problems requires people to step out of the narrow circle of the country and redefine national interests from the perspective of all mankind. The common interests of all mankind should be the basis for the formulation of a country's common foreign interests.

3.4 The rise of global environmental problems has raised the status of scientists in international politics.

In the traditional view of international politics, national leaders, diplomats, and generals play an important role, and the scientific community only plays a role behind the scenes. Since the Second World War, the status of scientists' groups has risen in international politics. The activities and research results of scientists are the necessary conditions for a country to participate in an international political field. For example, the necessary condition for participating in the Antarctic Treaty System is that substantive Antarctic exploration activities have been carried out, indicating that there is sufficient operational capacity in Antarctica. In today's globalization, the rise of global environmental problems has further raised the status of scientists in international politics.

"Usually, there is considerable scientific uncertainty about relevant issues, impacts and effective measures in international environmental politics." for example, although most scientists recognize the trend of global warming, the scientific community still has limited understanding of the climate system. The climate change prediction results only give the possible change trend and direction, including considerable uncertainty. Because of this, "scientific or expert knowledge often plays a very important role in environmental politics... Knowledge 'helps set the agenda, involves the mode of influence and power, and affects the definition of key actors' priorities and interests". With the rise of global environmental problems, only those

countries that have made considerable achievements in scientific research in relevant fields can have a voice and decision-making power in international politics in this field. At the same time, due to the uncertainty of science, there will be a marriage between "science" and politics in the field of relevant global environmental problems. There may be a political background behind science, and political will may pass through the scientific body.

3.5 The rise of global environmental problems requires international organizations to play a greater role.

The emergence of global environmental problems is a threat to the whole mankind, and solving global environmental problems is the common interest of the whole mankind. In this process, we cannot exclude sovereign states, which play an important role in solving global environmental problems. "The coordinated response of international agreements to environmental issues is important. Among them, diplomacy between countries must come to the front stage, and sovereign countries must be the legitimate signatories of any treaty." however, it is impossible to solve global environmental problems only by sovereign countries. "National decision-making has caused global pollution problems, but it is unable to solve pollution problems at the national level; solving these problems requires cooperation between countries and funding from international development institutions (such as the World Bank)". "The more global crises a country faces, the more it needs to establish international organizations and build international relations through international organizations." to solve global environmental problems, we must pay attention to the role of international organizations and establish and improve international mechanisms.

Intergovernmental organizations such as the United Nations and the International Monetary Fund have specific objectives and capabilities to solve international problems through institutionalized cooperation institutions. "Since the 1970s... The establishment and gradual improvement of the United Nations environmental mechanism has become an important symbol of the development of the United Nations mechanism." the United Nations and its specialized agencies UNEP, the United Nations Environment Program Council, the environment coordination committee and the GEF Management Committee have become the core organizations responsible for promoting environmental protection at the global level. Many global efforts to solve global environmental problems are carried out under the framework of the United Nations, which has done a lot of work in establishing an organizational system for coordinating, managing, and controlling global environmental problems. For example, organizing a global environment conference to discuss environmental issues, including climate warming, and convening the conference of the parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on climate change every year since 1995. Together with the World Meteorological Organization, organizing the Intergovernmental Panel on climate change to study climate change and issue assessment reports, to promote international environmental legislation, including global climate change, together with the world bank, it established the global environment facility (GEF) in 1990 to help developing countries solve global environmental problems. "Environmental protection policy has become a part of the

WTO rule system and has become the general trend." in the new round of trade negotiations, environmental protection should become an important topic. At the same time, the world bank and the International Monetary Fund can also play an extremely important role in solving the financial problem of global environmental problems.

Regional cooperation and regional integration play an important role in solving global environmental problems, typically the EU. As the most integrated regional organization in the world, the EU implements a unified environmental policy. It is also the most important driving force to solve global environmental problems. For example, the EU appears in the global climate change negotiations and assumes important responsibilities. It actively carries out international environmental cooperation with other countries. The EU has become the main force to promote the global climate change negotiations.

Some non-governmental organizations and international movements, especially those guided by the trend of Greenpeace, play an important role in the solution of global environmental problems. For example, Greenpeace, established in 1971 with the purpose of maintaining a green, peaceful, and sustainable future, is currently working on environmental protection in more than 40 countries. For another example, one after another "green movement" in the world strongly requires countries to protect the environment, so the Green Party International came into being.

In today's globalization, the rise of global environmental problems not only reflects the deterioration of human living environment, but also reflects human concern about this problem. However, because there is no authority above the state, no international political act can determine the decision-making of a sovereign state and require it to protect the environment. Due to the different levels of environmental protection and social development, it is difficult for countries to solve the problem of environmental security at the same time. Without the unified and coordinated action of all countries, this "tragedy of common land" cannot be avoided, and the public goods of good global environment cannot be provided. Therefore, at present, it is very difficult to solve the global environmental problems, which requires the unremitting efforts of the international community.

References

1. Al-Dahash, H. F., Thayaparan, M., & Kulatunga, U. (2016). Understanding the terminologies: Disaster, crisis and emergency. In: Chan, P.W. and Neilson, C.J. (Eds.) Proceedings of the 32nd Annual ARCOM Conference, 5–7 September 2016, Manchester, UK.
2. Birkland, T. A. (2006). Lessons of disasters. Policy change after catastrophic events. Georgetown University Press.
3. Boin, A., 't Hart, P., & McConnell, A. (2009). Crisis exploitation: Political and policy impacts of framing contests. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 16(1), 81–106.

4. Cottle, S. (2014). Rethinking media and disasters in a global age: What's changed and why it matters. *Media, War & Conflict*, 7(1), 3–22.
5. De Wilde, P. (2013). Representative claims analysis: Theory meets method. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 20(2), 278–294.
6. Environment Agency. (2018). Estimating the economic costs of the 2015 to 2016 winter floods.
7. Kaufmann, M., Lewandowski, J., Choryński, A., & Wiering, M. (2016). Shock events and flood risk management: A media analysis of the institutional long-term effects of flood events in the Netherlands and Poland. *Ecology and Society*, 21(4), 51–65.
8. Koopmans, R. (2007). Who inhabits the European public sphere? Winners and losers, supporters and opponents in Europeanised political debates. *European Journal of Political Research*, 46(2), 183–210.
9. Liefferink, D., Wiering, M., Crabbé, A., & Hegger, D. (2018). Explaining stability and change. Comparing flood risk governance in Belgium, France, the Netherlands, and Poland. *Journal of Flood Risk Management*, 11(3), 281–290.
10. Mair, P. (2007). Political opposition and the European Union. *Government and Opposition*, 42(1), 1–17.
11. Olsson, E. K., Nord, L. W., & Falkheimer, J. (2015). Media coverage crisis exploitation characteristics: A case comparison study. *Journal of Public Relations Research*, 27(2), 158–174.
12. Pantti, M. K., & Wahl-Jorgensen, K. (2011). 'Not an act of god': Anger and citizenship in press coverage of British man-made disasters. *Media, Culture and Society*, 33(1), 105–122.

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